

Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude and Practice on drug abuse among clinical students at Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University Amaku, Awka, Anambra State

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Abstract: Drug abuse is a rapidly growing global public health and social mayhem. Almost one out of every eight youth is a victim of drug abuse. Drug abuse is not strictly consumption of hard drugs like cocaine, marijuana etc. some over-the-counter drugs that contain caffeine, drugs that serve as analgesics and every other drug can be abused. This is because drug abuse is simply the wrong use of drugs. Hence, this study was carried out to assess the knowledge, attitude and practice of clinical students of COOU teaching hospital towards drug abuse. This study employed the use of observational descriptive cross-sectional method and a self-structured questionnaire containing 28 close-ended questions was used to acquire data from all clinical students of COOU Teaching Hospital Awka. The data collected was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. From the result, it can be seen that 117 (79.6%) of the clinical students were considered to have a good knowledge about drug abuse with the sum of 13.87 ± 3.05 . Cocaine was reported to be known in 100% of participants followed by tramadol and cough syrup respectively, while 59.2% of participants knew amphetamine. 65.9% of the clinical students believe that drug abuse can lead to death. 45.9% of them gain their knowledge from social media. 80.9% reported that drug abuse can lead to psychiatric problems. 72.8% think drug abuse is treatable. Also, 60.5% of the participants have poor attitudes toward drug abuse. 22.8% of the participants see that drug addicts are more criminal than the victims. 73 (49.7%) of the participants believe that drug abuse is a problem in COOU Teaching Hospital Awka, Anambra state, whereas 15 (10.2%) say that it is not. In the case of practice, 53 (36.1%) have good practice with a sum of 2.7 ± 1.33 . 83 out of 144 clinical students (56.5%) read about drug abuse but only 21 clinical students (14.3%) participated in the treatment of drug abused patients before. Moreover, 37 (25.2%) participants advised abused patients. Using cross-tabulation and the Chi-square test, the association between knowledge, attitude, and practice with gender, age, level, and marital status were all studied. There was a significant association between gender and practice score ($p = 0.044$). Also, between level and with knowledge ($p < 0.001$), attitude ($p = 0.001$) and practice scores ($p < 0.001$). In conclusion, there is need to improve the dissemination of information on drug abuse as there is very poor attitude and practice towards drug abuse among the clinical students of COOU Teaching Hospital Awka.

Keywords: drug, drug abuse, consumption, wrong.

1. INTRODUCTION

Drugs are implied to construct not to crush, to restore not to destroy and to mend not to deplete. They are substances competent of causing an alteration within the biological system of a being through its chemical activities, whilst adjusting discernments, cognition, temperament, conduct and overall body functions. However, latest indignation within the nation, focuses to the exceptional truth that most drugs have gotten to be severally mal-handled and abused, through wrongful and improper application, thus coming about in a national or worldwide menace (11) According to the World Health

Organization, a psychoactive substance is any chemical substance which modifies physical and/or mental ability. (5) Drug abuse or substance abuse alludes to the exploit of certain chemicals for the reason of making pleasurable impacts on the brain. (1) Agreeing to the Demonstrative and Factual Manual of Mental Disarranges, Fifth Version (DSM-5), substance abuse is characterized as the exploit of any drug, in a way that goes astray from endorsed social or therapeutic designs. (5) The expanding generation, dissemination, advancement and simple accessibility of substance along with the changing values of society has come about in rising substance abuse related issues rising as a major global public health concern. (2,3,4,5)

Drug abuse is rising as a worldwide public health and social issue with changing indigenous conditions and issues. (3,10) The 2019 world drug report of the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) evaluated that 271 million (5.5%) of the worldwide populace (between ages of 15 and 64), had consumed drugs within the past year, it has been anticipated that 35 million people will be encountering drug abuse. (7) Around 5% of the worldwide grown-up populace reports utilizing at slightest one unlawful drug though 14% of the world's populace smokes cigarettes, and roughly 42% devours liquor. (5) A report from United Nations Office on Drugs and Crimes (UNODC) said around 275 million people used drugs around the world within the previous year, whereas over 36 million individuals experienced drug use disorders, concurring to the 2021 world drug report discharged by the UNODC. As the 2018 National Drug Utilize Overview uncovered, in Nigeria at that time there were around 14.3 million drug clients of which near to three million endured from a drug utilize clutter. (9) In Nigeria, the burden of drug abuse is on the rise and getting to be a open wellbeing concern. Nigeria, which is the foremost crowded nation in Africa, has created a notoriety as a center for drug trafficking and utilization generally among the youth populace. (7) Agreeing to the 2018 UNODC report "Drug utilize in Nigeria". The to begin with large-scale, across the nation national drug utilize overview in Nigeria, one in seven people (matured 15–64 a long time) had used a drug within the past year. (8) Nigeria is a massively diverse nation with over 400 ethnicities and numerous religious beliefs. Drug abuse is hence seen inside a broader setting in Nigeria, due to its multicultural nature. Just like most social orders don't consider the consumption of some drugs which do not create obvious behavioral changes as drug abuse. In any case, in spite of this multicultural nature of the Nigerian populace, there's a reliable clamor from both the public, police, ministers, health professionals, instructors, administrative offices and guardians on the developing burden of drug abuse (abuse of drugs which influence behavior) within the nation. (7)

Notwithstanding, within the setting of this investigate, drug abuse is considered as taking overdose of a particular drug or substance; or aimless utilization of such substances competent of annoying the natural working and physiological conduct of people devouring them. (3) Substance abuse leads to substance habit with the improvement of resilience and reliance. Resilience refers to a condition where the client needs higher dose of the drug to encounter the same effect. Smaller amounts, which were adequate prior, are not viable and the client is constrained to extend the sum of drug admissions. Gradually, drug reliance develops. Both substance abuse and reliance require a maladaptive design of substance utilization. (2)

Medical education has continuously been respected as profoundly demanding. In spite of the fact that, as it were the academically-minded youth within the society tend to be chosen for medical education, the upsetting scholarly environment can apply a negative impact on the mental and physical well-being of clinical students. (4) Clinical students, as future specialists, hold a special status in society and gain benefits and duties diverse from those of other understudies. Various guidelines of proficient behavior are subsequently anticipated from them. (6) A major stressor for medical education is the sum and complexity of the information to be learned. Relationship with specialists, fear of disappointment, family issues, instability with respect to supervisor's desires and vulnerabilities with respect to performance are a few of the components contributing to mental trouble among clinical students. (4) In any case, substance usage by clinical students presents dangers and can too have genuine results on their adequacy and wellness to hone as tomorrow's specialists. It is accepted that substance consumption among doctors begin early in their careers and the significance of learning the ways of life of clinical students to note substance abuse is well recognized (6)

Hence, this study is to ascertain the knowledge, attitude, and practice of Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University Teaching Hospital Clinical students on drug abuse.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study is an observational descriptive cross-sectional study conducted among clinical students of Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu teaching hospital Awka in Anambra State, Nigeria from the 15th of September 2022 to the 22nd of September 2022.

Participants

This study included all clinical students of Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu teaching hospital Awka, Anambra State. All clinical students who refused to participate were excluded from the study.

Instruments used in the study:

A self-structured questionnaire containing 28 close-ended questions adopted from relevant studies in the English language that takes about 5 minutes to complete was used to fulfill the objectives of the study.

The questionnaire was divided into four parts:

Part 1: contain four questions regarding socio-demographic data including gender, age, level, and marital status; Part 2: contain five questions regarding knowledge about drug abuse; Part 3: contain five questions regarding attitude towards drug abuse while Part 4: contain six questions regarding practice in the drug abuse. The questionnaire used was structured upon published literature and had no definitive standard or validated score. Therefore, suitable scores were used to have a better assessment of overall knowledge, attitude, and practice toward drug abuse.

Data collection and Sampling:

Survey sampling was conducted to acquire the responses from the participants via face to face during the study period. The total sample size of 147 was selected using Yamane formular as shown in equation 1 below. The purpose of the study was explained to each student, and those students who agreed to participate in the study were included. 147 students out of 200 were included in the study.

Sample size calculation:

To calculate the sample size the following equation was used

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(0.05)^2} \tag{1}$$

With population size 200 and 0.05 margin of error, a sample of 134 can be considered as a minimal sample to represent the population. By adding 10% of the sample size, the sample size reached 147.

Statistical analysis:

Initially, the data collected as from the questionnaire were organized into an excel spreadsheet. The data is then transferred and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. The data analysis was cleaned and analyzed. Descriptive statistics and summary measures, data display in tables. Both descriptive and inferential statistics are involved. A Chi-square test was used to find associated factors. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3. RESULTS

Participants' information:

Of all 147 participants, 68 (47.3%) were females, while 79 (53.7%) are males. The mean age of the participants (standard deviation) is 21.83 (2.053) ranging between the minimum of 23 and a maximum of 40 years. 134 (91.2%) were unmarried and 13 (8.8%) live with family. Forth year students, fifth year and final-year students participated in different percent (n = 51,47,49, (34.7%, 31.9%, 33.3%) for each). Others baseline characteristics for the included clinical students were shown in (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the respondents

Variables	Category	N=147 (%)
Gender	Male	79 (53.7%)
	Female	68 (47.3%)
Age	23-25	43(29.3%)
	26-28	60(40.8%)

	29-31	19 (12.9%)
	32-34	13(8.80%)
	35-37	8(5.40%)
	38-40	4(2.70%)
Academic Level		
	4 TH	51 (34.7%)
	5 TH	47 (31.9%)
	Final year	49 (33.3%)
Marital Status		
	Married	13 (8.80%)
	Single	134 (91.2%)
Knowledge Score level		
	Good Knowledge	117 (79.6%)
	Poor Knowledge	30 (21.4%)
Attitude Score level		
	Good Attitude	58 (39.5%)
	Poor Attitude	89 (60.5%)
Practice Score level		
	Good practice	53 (36.1%)
	Poor practice	94 (63.9%)
Knowledge sum score	13.87 ± 3.05	
Attitude sum score	4.76 ± 1.24	
Practice sum score	2.7 ± 1.33	

Knowledge of the students about drugs abuse

117 (79.6%) of the clinical students were considered to have a good knowledge about drug abuse with the sum of 13.87 ± 3.05 (Table 1). Cocaine was reported to be known in 100% of participants followed by tramadol and cough syrup respectively, while 59.2% of participants knew amphetamine. 65.9% of the clinical students believe that drug abuse can lead to death. While 45.9% of them gained their knowledge from social media. 80.9% reported that drug abuse can lead to psychiatric problems. Lastly 72.8% think drug abuse is treatable. More details can be seen in (Table 2).

Table 2: Knowledge about drug abuse among participants

Variables	Response	N (%)
Are you aware of the following drug abuse?		
Cough syrup	Yes	106 (72.1%)
	No	41 (27.9%)
Tramadol	Yes	123 (83.7%)
	No	24 (16.3%)
Cocaine	Yes	147(100%)
	No	-
Amphetamine	Yes	87 (59.2%)
	No	60 (40.8%)
What is your source of knowledge about the drug abuse?		
Friends	Yes	46 (31.3%)
Relatives	Yes	22 (14.9%)
Social media	Yes	67 (45.6%)
TV	Yes	12 (8.2%)

Can Drug abuse cause death		
Yes	=====	97 (65.9%)
No	=====	09 (6.1%)
I don't know	=====	40 (27.2%)
Can Drug abuse cause psychiatric problems		
Yes	=====	119 (80.9%)
No	=====	---
I don't know	=====	28 (19.1%)
Is drug abuse treatable?		
Yes	=====	107 (72.8%)
No	=====	---
I don't know	=====	40 (27.2%)

Attitudes of clinical students towards abused patients and drug abuse

Of all participants, 89 (60.5%) have a (poor) attitudes toward drug abuse with a sum of 4.7 ± 1.2 (Table 1). Of all, 33 (22.8%) of the participants see that drug addicts are more criminal than the victims. 73 (49.7%) of the participants believe that drug abuse is a problem to us here in Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu teaching hospital Awka, Anambra state, whereas 15 (10.2%) say that it is not. More details about the attitudes of clinical students in Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu teaching hospital Awka, Anambra State were shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Attitudes towards abused patients and drug abuse among participants. (n = 147)

Question	Agree	Undecided	Disagree
Our society is too forgiving toward drug user	27 (18.4%)	67 (45.6%)	53 (36.1%)
Drug abuse is more as criminal than the victim	33 (22.4%)	51 (34.7%)	63 (42.9%)
I tend to avoid someone who is a drug addict	83 (56.5%)	17 (11.6%)	47 (31.9%)
Drug abuse is not given a fair chance to get along in society	61 (41.5%)	67 (45.6%)	19 (12.9%)
Drug abuse is not a problem to us here in Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu teaching hospital Awka	15 (10.2%)	59 (40.1%)	73 (49.7%)

The practice of clinical students towards abused patients and drug abuse:

Of all participants, 53 (36.1%) have good practice with a sum of 2.7 ± 1.33 (Table 1). 83 out of 144 clinical students (56.5%) read about drug abuse but only 21 clinical students (14.3%) participated in the treatment of drug abused patients before. Moreover, 37 (25.2%) participants advised abused patients. Further information about the practice were shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Practice toward abused patients and drug abuse among participants. (n = 147)

Variables	N=147
The practice of clinical students toward abused patients and drug abuse	77 (52.4%)
Tried illegal drug (Yes)	42 (28.6%)
Read about drugs abuse (Yes)	83 (56.5%)
Advised drug abused patients (Yes)	37 (25.2%)
Participated in treatment (Yes)	21 (14.3%)

KAP scores and association between socio-demographic variables:

Using cross-tabulation and the Chi-square test, the association between knowledge, attitude, and practice with gender, age, level, and marital status were all studied. There was a significant association between gender and practice score ($p = 0.044$). Also, between level and with knowledge ($p < 0.001$), attitude ($p = 0.001$) and practice scores ($p < 0.001$) (Table 5).

Table 5: Association of knowledge, attitude, and practice of drug addiction with socio-demographic characteristics

Variables	Knowledge		p-value	Attitude		p-value	Practice		p-value
	Good	Poor		Good	Poor		Good	Poor	
Gender									
Male	49	30		24	55		39	40	

Female	49	19	0.074	37	31	0.052	43	25	0.038
Age									
23-25	20	8	0.004	10	20	0.003	09	22	0.000
26-28	40	19		11	23		14	19	
29-31	16	05		14	06		05	18	
32-34	09	05		06	13		07	13	
35-37	10	02		03	15		10	03	
38-40	07	06		07	20		11	16	
Level									
3 rd year	32	19	0.033	21	30	0.001	08	43	0.021
4 th year	31	16		15	32		11	36	
5 TH year	35	14		18	31		23	26	
Marital Status									
Single	93	15	0.055	87	21	0.103	78	30	0.061
Married	17	22		26	13		24	15	

4. DISCUSSION

The present study was an institutional descriptive cross-sectional study conducted on 147 clinical students, enrolled to assess knowledge, attitude, and practice of drug abuse among the clinical students at the teaching hospital Awka Anambra state.

147 students were approached in this study, the age of participants ranged from 23 to 40 years >, in which 43 (29.3%) of the participant are within 23-25 and 26-28 years is 60 (40.8%) which is considered as the young active age. Most of the participants were males who accounted for 79(53.9%) while females accounted for only 68 (47.3%) of the clinical students. This is reflecting the real majority of males in the teaching hospital. Regarding their academic level, most of the participants were in 4th level having 51 (34.7%) participants, followed by the final year student having 49 (33.3%) participants.

The majority of participating students were single 134 (91.2%) and only a few percent 13 (8.8%) of participants were married. Regarding the knowledge about drug abuse, most of the students were familiar with most type of drug abuse. Cocaine was found to be the most kind knew followed by tramadol, then cough syrup, then amphetamine.

Of the 147 clinical students, most were considered to have good knowledge about drug abuse (79.6%). This is not a surprising result as it is conducted in a teaching hospital among clinical students. Similarly, of all participants, 89 (60.5%) have a (poor) attitudes toward drug abuse with a sum score of (4.7 ± 1.2) while 53 (36.1%) have good practice with a sum score of (2.7 ± 1.33).

5. CONCLUSION

Drugs are substances that alter the biological system. There have been rampant cases of illicit consumption of drugs and usage of overly harsh, hard and socially banned drugs across the world most especially among adolescents and adults of below 60 years. Advanced/old patients of drug abuse are as a result of wrong use of drugs at their younger age. According to report, great portion of the world’s population not withstanding academic or professional qualification are victims of drug abuse. It has been observed that even among clinical students, the case of drug abuse is still in occurrence. Therefore, there is need to share the knowledge among the clinical students so as to improve their attitude and practice towards drug abuse.

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